

Unusual Properties of Complex Conditional Quantum Probability

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In quantum mechanics, a free electron is described by $\exp(i(kx-wt))$ where $E = \hbar w = (\hbar k)^2/2m$. This has the math form of a "wave". If, on the other hand, one tries to define a complex conditional probability for a bound electron in the following manner:

$$P(p/x) = [fp \exp(ipx)] / [\text{Sum on } p \text{ } fp \exp(ipx)] \quad ((1))$$

some unusual properties of this probability arise. The purpose of this note is to try to examine these.

Periodic $\exp(ipx-Et)$

The function $\exp(ikx)$ is periodic and can be thought of as a rotating unit radius. If one uses $\exp(ipx)$ in a definition of probability such as ((1)), two features may be noticed:

1. The probability contains two parts that average independently, but are linked $\cos(kx)$ and $\sin(kx)$ from $\cos(kx)+i\sin(kx)$
2. Both $\cos(kx)$ and $\sin(kx)$ may be positive or negative and are periodic.

For example, for a free electron $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1 = \cos^2(px) + \sin^2(px)$. This has the appearance of an "or" probability. If one uses $\exp(ipx)$ in probability, it seems one needs an explanation of these two features. First, there are two parts to the probability which are separated by "i", but are interlinked as the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ is 1. Both parts are periodic ($\cos(kx)$ and $\sin(kx)$) and can be both positive and negative. In models of zitterbewegung, one has the electron undergoing spiral motion along its axis of motion. Thus, one might argue that these two features are present. In one dimensional models, one may have an electron bouncing back and forth while moving in one direction with an average p . Thus, it might be possible to have a complicated type of physical motion conform to $\exp(ipx)$.

There are, however, other issues. In the case of a bound state where there is symmetry such as $f(p)=f(-p)$, this leads to some puzzling results. For example:

$$\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } P(p/x) \text{ } p = [\text{Sum over } p>0 \text{ } p \text{ } i^2 \sin^2(px)] / [\text{Sum over } p>0 \text{ } 2 \cos^2(px)] \quad ((2))$$

And

$$\langle p^*p \text{ conditional} \rangle = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^*p P(p/x) = [\text{Sum over } p>0 \text{ } p^*p 2 \cos(px)] / [\text{Sum over } p>0 \cos(px)] \quad ((3))$$

One may notice immediately that p to an odd power ((2)) uses $\sin(px)$ in the numerator average, while p to an even power ((3)) uses $\cos(px)$. This is strange because usually one has a distribution function, such as in the Boltzmann equation, with $f(x,p)$ used to average any function of x and p . Here the odd function picks up one function $\sin(kx)$, while the even picks up another, $\cos(kx)$. This is unusual as the conditional averages may be related to physical quantities. For example, ((2)) the average momentum flow is related to the change in density with x , a measurable:

$$d/dx W(x)W(x) = 2 W(x)W(x) [dW(x)/dx / W(x)] \text{ where } dW/dx / W(x) \text{ is proportional to } \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle. \quad ((4))$$

Where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } f p \exp(ipx)$.

Similarly,

$$-1/2m [d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) = .5m v(x)v(x) \text{ where } v(x) \text{ is the classical kinetic energy is proportional to } \langle p^*p \text{ conditional} \rangle. \quad ((5))$$

Thus, it seems there are two components to the probability ($\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$) and for even p power conditional averages, the $\sin(px)$ piece cancels because $\sin(-px) = -\sin(px)$, while for odd p powers, $\cos(px)$ cancels, leaving $\sin(px)$. Thus, it seems that experiments set up to measure p odd or p even power quantities would deal with different “physical” aspects of the probability. This is unusual, because one would expect that if one knows probabilities for p at x , one would simply square p and use the same probability to calculate conditional averages. That is not the case in quantum mechanics. Furthermore, the system may “sense” an odd power average using $\sin(px)$, and at the same time “sense” the even power average using $\cos(px)$, thus, there is a link between the two averages (which describe different physical phenomena.) One uses $\sin(px)$ at a point x , while the other uses $\cos(px)$ for all p . It is almost as if there is a kind of entanglement between the even and odd p power averages.

For example, taking the spatial derivative of the time independent Schrodinger equation yields:

$$-1/2m [d/dx d/dx d/dx W(x)] / W(x) + 1/2m \{W(x) d/dx d/dx W(x)\} [d/dx \ln(W)] = \text{Force}(x) \quad ((6))$$

The first term on the LHS uses $\sin(px)$ in the numerator as does $[d/dx \ln(W)]$ while $\{W(x) d/dx d/dx W(x)\}$ uses $\cos(px)$. The latter two are both related to physical phenomena it seems and Force itself is physical.

In addition, when one takes an average using $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$, it does not seem that $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$ disappears, one of the other just does not contribute to the average depending on whether p is to an even or odd power.

Furthermore, because $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are periodic, the numerator of the average e.g. $\sum \cos^2(px)$ and $\sum \sin^2(px)$ are both periodic. If divided by $W(x)$ which may also be periodic, one may obtain a smooth function. For example, ((5)) is equal to $.5m v(x)v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity and this is not periodic in x for many problems. For example, an oscillator wavefunction for $n > 1$ may be highly periodic in x , but $v(x)$ is not.

High Energy Limit and $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ averages

One may ask what happens in the high energy limit in which quantum mechanics is supposed to be similar to classical physics. $\langle \cos^2(px) \rangle$ uses $\sin(px)$ in the numerator and $\langle \sin^2(px) \rangle$ uses $\cos(px)$. Both averages are different, but the integral of density $\langle \cos^2(px) \rangle$ is the same as $\langle \sin^2(px) \rangle$.

$$d/dx [W(x) d/dx W(x)] = W(x) d/dx d/dx W(x) + [d/dx W] [d/dx W] \quad ((6))$$

If $W(x)=0$ at the endpoints, the LHS is 0 and:

$$-W(x) d/dx d/dx W(x) = [d/dx W] [d/dx W] = W(x)W(x) [d/dx \ln(W)] [d/dx \ln(W)]. \quad ((7))$$

As pointed out in (1), if a function (such as an oscillator function) becomes highly periodic (with a high frequency), each endpoint of the hump of $W(x)W(x)=\text{density}$ is 0. Thus ((6)) should apply to this case as well, but the hump is so small, one does not have integrate, but only evaluate the function. Thus, $\langle \cos^2(px) \rangle$ approximates the square root of $\langle \sin^2(px) \rangle$ and this in turn is proportional to $v(x)$, the classical velocity. Thus, at the high energy limit, the $\cos(kx)$ and $\sin(kx)$ differences lead to the same overall result, at least for $\langle \cos^2 \rangle$ and $\langle \sin^2 \rangle$. $\langle \cos^2 \rangle$ becomes the same as $v(x)$ which is the rms velocity result, within the little hump of $W(x)W(x)$.

Conclusion

Quantum mechanics makes heavy use of the form $\exp(ipx)$, which represents the wavefunction of a free quantum particle, such as an electron. If one uses $\exp(ipx)$ as part of the conditional probability $P(p/x) = [\sum \exp(ipx)] / W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum \exp(ipx)$, then the probability is complex (i.e. has two linked components which “average” separately, namely $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$). These are linked, but $\cos(px)$ (in the numerator) remains for even p power functions and $\sin(px)$ for odd p powers. These averages may represent physical entities so the

different averages are linked or entangled in a sense. Furthermore, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are periodic and this affects the averages as well. It seems that if one wishes to consider seriously the idea of $P(p/x)$, one needs to think of $\exp(ipx)$ in terms of a complicated motion (such as zitterbewegung) which could give rise to a conditional probability of the form $(\cos(px), \sin(px))$ with the two components averaging independently.

References

Ruggeri, Francesco R. Cramer Rao Inequality for Fisher Information and Zeros of the Wavefunction (preprint, zenodo, 2019)